

curves. The values were computed using the above computational techniques and the mean values are presented in Table 1. The metal-ligand stability constants decrease with an increase in the ionic strength of the media is in accordance with Hückel's theory¹⁰.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Ln(III) COMPLEXES AT 25° AND DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS

Cations	log K ₁	μ=0.35M	μ=0.2M	μ=0.05M	μ=0.00M
H ⁺	log K ₁ ^H	11.46±0.06	11.59±0.04	11.80±0.08	—
La ³⁺	log K ₁ ^H	9.27±0.03	9.29±0.03	9.45±0.08	—
	log K ₁	8.05±0.05	8.42±0.03	9.12±0.03	9.60
Ce ³⁺	log K ₁	7.51±0.06	7.46±0.02	8.20±0.09	8.60
	log K ₂	9.18±0.01	9.68±0.02	9.96±0.02	10.40
Pr ³⁺	log K ₁	8.25±0.05	8.46±0.03	9.09±0.05	9.50
	log K ₂	8.63±0.02	8.99±0.01	9.65±0.02	10.20
Nd ³⁺	log K ₁	7.93±0.02	8.04±0.06	8.74±0.01	9.25
	log K ₂	9.07±0.07	9.49±0.01	10.00±0.04	10.58
Sm ³⁺	log K ₁	8.10±0.04	8.26±0.03	9.01±0.05	8.60
	log K ₂	9.41±0.05	9.99±0.04	10.36±0.04	11.00
Gd ³⁺	log K ₁	8.59±0.06	9.11±0.02	9.44±0.02	9.90
	log K ₂	9.21±0.03	9.70±0.01	10.36±0.04	10.98
Tb ³⁺	log K ₁	8.50±0.00	8.55±0.03	9.26±0.02	9.73
	log K ₂	9.58±0.05	9.89±0.03	10.50±0.04	11.11
Dy ³⁺	log K ₁	8.84±0.04	9.31±0.06	9.78±0.05	10.20
	log K ₂	9.46±0.04	9.93±0.05	10.39±0.07	10.95
Ho ³⁺	log K ₁	8.77±0.04	9.23±0.03	9.61±0.05	10.00
	log K ₂	9.61±0.05	10.26±0.04	10.54±0.05	11.20
Y ³⁺	log K ₁	9.00±0.05	9.41±0.06	9.80±0.05	10.30
	log K ₂	9.11±0.05	9.69±0.07	10.37±0.03	11.08
	log K ₃	8.45±0.05	8.89±0.05	9.56±0.01	10.11

Linear plots were observed when log K_n values were plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$. Thermodynamic step stability constants (Table 1) were obtained by extrapolating the experimentally determined stability constants to zero ionic strength. A more or less increasing trend of stability constants was observed with decreasing ionic radii for lighter lanthanides. The only exception was with Ce(III), and this anomalous behaviour is probably due to the tendency of cerium towards quadrivalency. Stability order shows a break at or very near Gd³⁺ ion which has been interpreted as corresponding to either the stability of the half-filled (4f⁷) arrangement for Gd³⁺ ion or the change in ionic radii centering at the Gd³⁺ ion which allows a change in the coordination number of the cation^{1,12}. The heavier lanthanides do not show a regular trend as has been observed in a number of systems¹².

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Formation Constants of the Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidine-*p*-Acetylaminoaniline with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Mg²⁺ with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidine-*p*-acetylaminoaniline. The dissociation constants of the ligand and formation constants of its metal chelates have been determined by Bjerrum's method at 25±0.1°, and at ionic strength 0.1M NaClO₄ in 75:25 (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The order of stability of chelates is found to be Cu>Zn>Co>Ni>Mg.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidine-*p*-acetylaminoaniline was prepared by adding an equimolar quantity of *p*-acetylaminoaniline to 10 gm of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol and refluxing the reaction mixture on a water bath for an hour. After cooling, the solution was filtered to give the crude product which was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to get an analytically pure compound having m.p. 139° (observed). (Found: C, 74.10; H, 5.20; N, 9.05 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆N₂O₃; C, 74.02; H, 5.19; N, 9.09 per cent) and C=N stretching frequency, 1624 cm⁻¹.

The experimental techniques used in the present investigation were the same as reported earlier^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by the rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titrations and

by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after two hrs. This was also corroborated by taking TLC from time to time of a sample titration mixture.

In the ligand, it is the chelated phenolic (OH) group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one. For the proton ligand complexes, $\bar{n}_A$ is defined as the average number of protons bound per uncomplexed ligand. From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and plotted against 'B'. The plot extended over the range $0.48 < \bar{n}_A < 1.70$

Fig. 1. Titration curves 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidine-p-acetyl-aminoaniline. Plot of 'B' vs volume of NaOH(ml).

and was wavelike. The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H were evaluated from half integral points at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values so obtained were further corroborated by straight line plots of $\log [\bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)]$ vs B, and $\log [(2 - \bar{n}_A) / (\bar{n}_A - 1)]$ vs B respectively.

From the metal-ligand titration curves, $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against pL to get the formation curves of the metal complex equilibria. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated from these curves at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. These values were further corroborated from the straight line plots.

$\log K_2$ values for Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} could not be obtained due to the precipitation, possibly due to hydrolysis. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of $\log K_1$ values in the present investigation has been found to be $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$. The higher stability constant of Cu^{2+} complex, than what would be expected from its electronegativity, arises possibly due to Jahn-Teller distortion⁸.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDINE-p-ACETYL-AMINOANILINE WITH Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} AND Mg^{2+} AT 25° IN 75% (v/v) DIOXAN-WATER AND AT IONIC STRENGTH 0.1M $NaClO_4$

Cations	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
Log K_1	10.80	11.00	7.66	5.93	5.63	5.20
Log K_2	3.60	7.60	—	—	—	4.63

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species LH and LH_2^+ while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 respectively.

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Studies of Rare Earths with Salicylhydroxamic Acid

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PREVIOUS studies with salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA), $o-C_6H_4(OH).CONHOH$ have illustrated the exceptional versatility of this chelating agent¹⁻⁸ forming the usual five-membered ring hydroxamic acid complexes.